

SIMPLIFIED SOLUTION TO DESIGN DFA, THAT ACCEPT STRINGS OVER {A,B} HAVING AT LEAST X NUMBER OF 'A' OR Y NUMBER OF 'B' COMMON BETWEEN TWO CONDITION.

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ABSTRACT

Today, it is very difficult to understand the design concepts of deterministic machine. One question is arise? How it is possible to understand the concepts of deterministic machine in a very easy manner. In this paper, we have design a DFA and develop an method with suitable examples that how DFA machine works in a simply manner. For it, we consider that a DFA machine takes the input string {a, b} having at least x number of a or y number of b common between TWO condition. The objective of this paper to understand the concepts of deterministic machine in easy manner.

KEYWORD - DFA, Transition Table, Transition Table (TT)

I. INTRODUCTION

DFAs are a fundamental topic in computer science education. Besides being part of the standardized computer science curriculum, the concept of DFA is rich in structure and potential applications. It is useful in diverse settings such as control theory, text editors, lexical analyzers, and models of software interfaces.

A deterministic Finite automaton (also known as deterministic finite state machines) is the system to accomplish many tasks in Computer Science. To increase the computational power of existing computers, it is based not only to increase the frequency of CPU but also we use other modern technologies. The finite automata implementations are used to consider these types of technologies. For example, multiple CPU core is one of the latest technologies which is used now. We can represent DFA by digraphs which is also called state transition diagram. In this digraph the vertices are denoted by single circles of a transition diagram which represent the states of the DFA and the arcs are labeled with an input symbol correspond to the transitions. We represent accepting states by double circles.

Efficient learning of DFA is a challenging research problem in grammatical inference. It is known that both exact and approximate (in the PAC sense) identifiability of DFA is hard.

II. MYTHOLOGY

Automata theory is a branch of theoretical computer science, DFA is known as Deterministic Finite Automata. A finite state machine accepts or rejects finite strings of symbols and gives a unique computation for each input string[15]. McCulloch and Pitts were among the first

re-searchers to introduce a concept similar to finite automaton in 1943.[5]

A DFA is defined as an abstract mathematical concept, but due to the deterministic nature of a DFA, it is implementable in hardware and software for solving various specific problems[15]. For example, a DFA can model software that decides whether or not online user-input such as email addresses are valid.

Finite Automata (M) is defined as a set of five tuples (Q, Σ , δ , q, F)

0
Where

Q= a finite, non-empty set of states

Σ = a finite, non-empty set of inputs

δ is the state-transition function: $\delta: Q \times \Sigma \rightarrow Q$

q is the initial state

0

F is the set of final states, a subset of Q.

δ can be represents using either of three approach given below

• Transition Graph.

• Transition Function.

• Transition Table.

We had used the transition table as the approach to represent δ .

III. ALGORITHM

By applying this Algorithm we can design Deterministic Finite Automata that accept strings over input symbol a, b having atmost x number of a & y number of b

Algorithm to draw TG

Deterministic Finite Automata M= (Q, Σ , δ , q₀, F)

Where

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Q= {q₁₁,q₁₂,q₁₃,...,q₂₁,q₂₂,...,q_{ij}}

Σ = {a,b}

$\delta: Q \times \Sigma \rightarrow Q$ {Represented by Transition Graph }

Q₀ = q_{ij} when i=j and i=j=1. i.e. q₁₁

F={q₁₁,q₁₂,q₁₃,...,q₂₁,q₂₂,...,q_{ij}}

Let Q be the set of states in Deterministic Finite Automata such that $Q = \{q_{11}, q_{12}, q_{13}, \dots, q_{21}, q_{22}, \dots, q_{ij}\}$
 Where $i = 1$ to $x+1$
 $j = 1$ to $y+1$
 Input Symbol $\Sigma = \{a, b\}$
 q_{11} is the initial state.
 Design a directed transition graph having $(x+1) \cdot (y+1)$ states and mark all states as final states.
 Label each node as $q_{11}, q_{12}, q_{13}, \dots, q_{21}, q_{22}, \dots, q_{ij}$
 Where $i = 1$ to $x+1$; $j = 1$ to $y+1$; $x = na$ & $y = nb$
 FOR $i = 1$ to x
 do
 FOR $j = 1$ to y
 do
 if $i=j=1$ then $q_{ij} \in Q_0$ (Initial State)
 else there exist a edge E such that $\delta(q_{ij}, a) \rightarrow q_{ij+1}$
 done inner loop
 done outer loop
 FOR $i = 1$ to x
 do
 FOR $j = 1$ to y
 do
 if $i=j=1$ then $q_{ij} \in Q_0$ (Initial State)
 else there exist a edge E such that $\delta(q_{ji}, b) \rightarrow q_{j+1, i}$
 if $i=x+1$ and $j=y+1$ then there exist $\delta(q_{ij}, a) \rightarrow q_{ij}$ and $\delta(q_{ij}, b) \rightarrow q_{ij}$.
 done inner loop
 done outer loop
 q_{11} being the initial state
 DFA "M" will strings over input symbol a, b having atmost x number of a & y number of b if all the input is consumed and halting state is the final state.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Example 1:

Design a DFA, over a language $\{a, b, c\}$ which start with 'ab' and end with 'bc'.

Let the resultant DFA is $M = (Q, \Sigma, \delta, q_0, F)$
 Where

- $Q = \{q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4\}$
- $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$
- $\delta = Q \times \Sigma \rightarrow Q$
- $q_0 = \{q_0\}$
- $F = \{q_3\}$

Figure 1: DFA, over a language $\{a, b, c\}$ which start with 'ab' and end with 'bc'

TRANSITION TABLE:

M	a	b	c
q₀	q ₁	q _E	q _E
q₁	q _E	q ₂	q _E
q₂	q ₄	q ₂	q ₃
q₃	q ₄	q ₂	q ₄
q₄	q ₄	q ₂	q ₄
q_E	q _E	q _E	q _E

Example 2:

Design a DFA, over a language $\{p, q, r\}$ which start with 'pq' having sub string 'qpr' and end with 'rq'.

Let the resultant DFA is $M = (Q, \Sigma, \delta, q_0, F)$
 Where

- $Q = \{q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5, q_6, q_7\}$
- $\Sigma = \{p, q, r\}$
- $\delta = Q \times \Sigma \rightarrow Q$
- $q_0 = \{q_0\}$
- $F = \{q_5\}$

Figure 2: DFA, over a language $\{p, q, r\}$ which start with 'pq' having sub string 'qpr' and end with 'rq'.

TRANSITION TABLE

M	a	b	c
q₀	q ₁	q _E	q _E
q₁	q _E	q ₂	q _E
q₂	q ₃	q ₂	q ₆
q₃	q ₆	q ₂	q ₄
q₄	q ₇	q ₅	q ₄
q₅	q ₇	q ₇	q ₄
q₆	q ₆	q ₂	q ₆
q₇	q ₇	q ₇	q ₄
q_E	q _E	q _E	q _E

V. RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In the FIRST example - DFA, over a language $\{a, b, c\}$ which start with 'ab' and end with 'bc'.

Input symbol 'b' is common so, smallest accepted string over $\{a, b, c\}$ is **abc**.

RULE or CLUE:

Total number of states in DFA = total number of condition input symbol + 1(our side)

So, In this example **we should have 5 states.**

**But when we draw the basic DFA, it contain only 4 states,
Because 'b' is common.**

After solving we come to know that **1 state is miscellaneous.**

So, we have to keep in mind that whenever we are solving such problem, **one extra or miscellaneous state will come.**

In the SCECOND example - DFA,over a language {p,q,r} which start with 'pq' having sub string 'qpr' and end with 'rq'.

Input symbol 'q' and 'r' are common so, smallest accepted string over {p,q,r} is **pqprq.**

According to above **RULE or CLUE:**

**we should have 8 states.
But when we draw the basic DFA, it has only 6 states,
Because 'q' and 'r' are common.**

After solving we come to know that **2 state is miscellaneous.**

So, we have to keep in mind that whenever we are solving such problem, **two extra or miscellaneous state will come.**

VI. CONCLUSION

This research will definitely enhance the teaching learning environment of theory of computation and helps students to design DFA.

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